

Theoretical investigation into citizen science can help us understand the phenomenon better

Citizen Science has been gaining increasing attention and institutional support in Europe and around the world. However, the very term 'Citizen Science' and what it involves remains a matter of debate. The CS Track research team believes that while constraining ourselves to strict definitions might be limiting and unhelpful, a shared perspective is needed to better understand the phenomenon and help the citizen science field develop.

The European CS Track project has published a conceptual and theoretical framework of citizen science that includes a comprehensive literature review and a conceptual framework for analysing citizen science activities. This report will be instrumental in developing policy recommendations and best practice manuals.

Citizen science as a concept

The CS Track research team led by Christine Urban and Michael Strähle of Wissenschaftsladen Wien – Science Shop Vienna investigated and analysed citizen science as a concept to better understand the phenomenon. Some highlights of the report include:

- There is **no consensus about what the term 'citizen science' really means.**
- Citizen science is a rather undefined phenomenon that broadly refers to the active (or passive) **engagement of the public** in activities that are in some respect related to science and/or innovation, **excluding those members of the public who are (substantially) paid for it.**
- Oftentimes it is wrongly assumed that citizen scientists **lack formal qualifications for the scientific work that they are undertaking.**
- In citizen science communities, whose members are mostly scientists and scholars, a **power imbalance between professional scientists and people**

who have no academic education is often assumed, with the latter in the weaker position. However, this is not necessarily true.

- It is often assumed that citizen scientists are volunteers who engage in science projects, which is not necessarily accurate because:
 - in some cases, **scientists organising a project are not paid**, and thus volunteers like the citizen scientists.
 - in cases where citizen science is part of a curriculum, their **participation is obligatory**.
 - if one **gives one's opinion** in a public consultation one usually would **not use the term "volunteer" either**. Volunteering refers to working for a good cause rather than saying what one thinks about an issue.
- Definitions of citizen science can be clear and appropriate for specific purposes and specific activities. However, **we cannot expect a general definition of citizen science that suits all purposes**.
- For researchers analysing citizen science, potential funders or regulating bodies governing legal and ethical issues, **developing more clearly defined terminologies would ease talking about issues related to citizen science**.

Literature review on citizen science-related topics reveals knowledge gaps

There's an abundance of case studies, essays, reflections, and reports on citizen science projects and most of them are written by researchers directly involved in CS activities. On the other hand, systematic and comprehensive literature reviews and comparative analyses are scarce. Therefore, the CS Track research team conducted an extensive literature review and identified knowledge gaps including:

- There is not enough research about the **socio-economic and educational background of participants**, although the dominance of middle to upper class participants is widely accepted.
- There is a fundamental problem when citizen science claims to make science more democratic. When citizens are volunteers, their **possibilities to participate depends on their resources**. Time that is not needed to work for a living or to cut down living costs is a luxury the poor do not often possess.
- **Recognising citizen scientists' contributions** is a complex issue.
- The absence of adequate data regarding **participant demographics** limits not only our ability in drawing concrete conclusions about who participates

in citizen science projects but also in attending issues related to equity, diversity and inclusion.

- Current research has typically focused on the impact of individual projects, and only a few studies have investigated the **impact of citizen science** projects and public engagement in general.
- Our review regarding participant characteristics in citizen science has already shown that **reaching more diverse participants** in terms of their gender, age or socioeconomic status is certainly an area that **calls for more attention** and merits greater efforts if we wish to make citizen science more inclusive.
- There is a lack of research into integrating knowledge about the educational benefits of citizen science and how it can be inserted into learning settings.
- There is a lack of research into economic aspects of citizen science

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